

Leading Online Lesson Study: Brokering at the Boundaries

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This paper presents a critical reflection on the author's recent novel experience as a Lesson Study (LS) facilitator, where they acted as a boundary broker, using online LS as a boundary object to support the collaborative professional learning of a group of Irish primary teachers who taught in three different schools. The schools involved were part of an existing inter-school Shared Education partnership. The aim of the LS in this instance was to foster participants' achievement of agency by introducing them to online LS as a sustainable form of Professional Development (PD) which can support their collaborative practice within and between their schools. The author's critical reflection, which derives from their reflective diary and field notes, draws from Schön's (1983) notion of reflection-on-action, as well as Brookfield's (2016) critical lenses and is theoretically framed by emerging literature which proposes LS as a vehicle for teacher agency.

Introduction

Lesson Study (LS) describes a model of school-based Professional Development (PD) whereby a group of teachers research, plan, teach, observe and reflect on a lesson with a group of learners in a collaborative manner (Lewis et al., 2006). While the model originates in Japan, it has been adapted, adopted and contextualised by practitioners across the world (Seleznyov, 2018). Through its structured protocols and fundamentally collaborative nature, LS has been credited with enabling teachers to cross institutional, interpersonal and intrapersonal boundaries of practice (Akkerman & Bruining, 2016; Dudley et al., 2019), thus overcoming the relative isolation and insulation they often experience in their professional practice (Brosnan, 2014). The use of digital tools to conduct LS have become increasingly popular, particularly in instances where practitioners are dispersed (Hrastinski, 2021). During the recent COVID-19 pandemic, many LS practitioners found themselves forced to move their LS practice into the online space for the first time (e.g. Goei et al., 2021). The aim of the online LS in the present study was to foster participants' achievement of agency by introducing them to online LS as a sustainable form of PD which can support the participating teachers' collaborative practice within and between their schools.

Lesson Study as a Vehicle to Foster Teacher Agency

Teacher agency describes a teacher's ability to act with competence, purpose, autonomy and reflexivity within their own practice as well as within the wider social context (Priestly et al., 2016). Teacher agency is considered to be temporal, that is, constructed based on past beliefs, knowledge and experiences, enacted in the present and oriented towards the future (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998; Priestly et al., 2016). This paper adopts an ecological view of agency, which positions agency as contextualised and contingent on a complex interplay of individual actions within a broader social milieu (Biesta & Tedder, 2006). LS can be considered to serve as a vehicle to support teachers' achievement of agency in three key

ways: 1. Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK); 2. Collaborative expertise and 3. Professional community membership (Holden & Fotou, in review). PCK comprises the unique expertise required by teachers to engage in effective teaching. (Shulman, 1987). PCK is considered to be developed through activities within LS, which contribute to teachers' knowledge, for example, during the research phase, teachers have the opportunity to examine research about the particular subject or topic. Professional community membership relates to the nature of relational connections within the LS group. (Coburn & Russell, 2008; Lave & Wenger, 1991). This relates to the way LS protocols help to create a sociocultural learning space for teachers, where they learn through engaging in critical reflective dialogue, in line with Lave and Wenger's (1991) and Vygotsky's (1980) theories of situated and sociocultural learning. Collaborative expertise describes the ability to effectively engage within the context of a group, in order to share knowledge and ideas (Coburn & Russell, 2008). This is evident in LS where the teachers in the LS group leverage the experience and expertise of others within the group, for example, teachers from two different schools working together.

Lesson Study as a Boundary Object and Brokering Boundary Crossings

As teachers operationalise the factors of PCK, collaborative expertise and professional community membership, they engage in boundary crossing (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011). In the case of the study described in this paper, boundaries were institutional (between school sites), interpersonal (between each other) and intrapersonal (within themselves), in that individual participants belonged to three different school communities, and through engaging in LS, were invited to these multilevel boundaries in order to interact and engage with new ideas and practices (Akkerman & Bruining, 2016; Wenger-Trayner et al., 2015). Encounters at boundaries of practice are associated with risk, but also with growth and opportunity, as is the case when a boundary is crossed in order to engage in new learning (Akkerman & Bruining, 2016). Star (2010) suggests the term "boundary object" as a tool which enables boundary encounters and supports establishment of shared meaning across a boundary. In this instance, the structured protocols of LS served as a tool to establish shared meaning. The author's role was that of a "boundary broker" (Kubiak et al., 2015, p.81) who aimed to facilitate members of the LS groups in their negotiation of the various sociocultural and cognitive boundaries of their existing practice.

Overview and Context of the Project

The LS project described in this paper took place over the course of six months and involved six primary teachers in two parallel LS groups of three, with one representative teacher from each of the three schools in each group. All six teachers involved were teaching the same class level (5th class, pupils aged 10-12 years). While the initial intention was for the LS to take place in a face-to-face context, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic meant that the author was restricted to online facilitation only. Whilst relatively experienced in facilitating face-to-face LS as part of their role with a national support service, the project represented the author's first experience of online LS facilitation. Following receipt of ethical approval from the author's organisation and consent from relevant stakeholders, the two

groups were facilitated by the author to research, plan, teach and reflect on a research lesson with their classes in a collaborative manner. Both group lessons had a STEM curricular focus. LS meetings took place weekly on the Zoom platform, with each meeting lasting 60 to 90 minutes. A shared Google Drive folder was utilised to allow teacher participants to collaboratively create and share various LS materials. Each teacher was invited to video record their research lesson, and select up to three noteworthy moments from their taught lesson to play back and discuss with the other teachers in their group. The three schools involved in the study had enjoyed a successful history of collaboration as part of their involvement in a Shared Education partnership¹. However, in line with much of the literature pertaining to Shared Education partnerships (e.g. Donnelly, 2012; Loader & Hughes, 2017) teachers and school leaders in the three schools reported that much of the focus to date had been on pupil contact and collaboration. Part of their rationale for agreeing to take part in the LS project was to explore its potential for enhancing professional collaboration and sharing of knowledge between teachers in each of the schools.

Critical Reflections on Brokering Boundary Crossing in Online Lesson Study

In the next section, I reflect on some examples of the challenges I encountered as an online LS facilitator and multilevel boundary broker. I discuss how I tried to address these during the project, drawing on the lenses of self-dialogue and literature (Brookfield, 2016) to try to make sense of what I experienced.

Broker as a Vulnerable Marginal Stranger

As part of my facilitation of the two LS groups as earlier described, I found myself occupying multiple roles, for example, fellow teacher, researcher, facilitator, knowledgeable other (Lewis et al., 2006). Effective brokers are expected to address and articulate meanings and perspectives of the intersecting practices of daily teaching, of teacher education and of educational research (Akkerman & Bruining, 2016). This brokering role left me faced with a constant challenge of how to make the practice of one community relevant to another, whilst staying true to the LS process. In some instances, the process of negotiation was relatively straightforward. For example, reflecting on my successful initial phone calls with each school I noted “The principals’ ...positive perceptions of educational research in my discussions with them was notable- they showed a great level of support and interest, despite my being essentially a stranger!” [Reflective diary entry, pre-project phone calls with principals]. This resonated with the requirement to retain the role of marginal stranger “who sort of belongs and who sort of doesn’t” (Tinggaard, 2007, p.460). Akkerman and Bakker (2011) contend that this ambiguous position demanded of brokers is necessary for them to serve as actors in innovations.

¹ Shared Education is a programme which runs in Northern Ireland and the Border region of the Republic of Ireland, whose aim is to develop positive relations between Protestant and Catholic schools.

I felt my experience as a broker resonated with Kubiak et al. (2015, p.82) who suggest, in that “even if enough of an insider to have the legitimacy to be listened to, they must also remain outward facing so as to offer a different perspective which provides value to the community”. However, following initial buy-in, the negotiation with teachers and school leaders in practice proved challenging and demanded considerable personal flexibility and compromise, as is evidenced in the following example.

“The proposed approach [from principals] is for two parallel lesson studies to run within the partnership. This will involve two morning meetings and two afternoon meetings. I don’t know how I’m going to manage my own energy levels doing that! However I was eager to facilitate the schools and felt obliged to go along with their suggestion.” [Reflective diary entry, initial planning meeting with principals and teacher participants]

This example highlights the relative vulnerability of the broker, and resonates with Kubiak et al. (2015) who point out the demand for brokers at times to sacrifice their own power in order support achievement of collective agency.

Trust and Rapport in the Online Space

A further challenge I identified was the difficulty of creating the necessary micro-climate of trust and rapport for the participants to interact meaningfully in the online space (Kubiak et al., 2015). I noted that “With Zoom, you either say it to everyone or no one! ...Can the online space allow for meaningful or effective facilitation? Especially when I don’t know the teachers and have never met them” [Reflective diary entry, prior to first meeting with participants]. In order to establish trust, rapport and to establish a shared sense of meaning, I relied heavily on the structured protocols of LS as a boundary object. Drawing from expertise of LS colleagues who had previously engaged in LS online (e.g. Goei et al., 2021), I created an instructional online LS booklet which was shared with all participants prior to commencing the LS project. This booklet offered a clear and systematic structure to each meeting, including prompt questions to guide discussion. As part of each meeting, a timekeeper and note taker were nominated, in order to give the teacher participants a sense of ownership over the project. While I was perceived as a knowledgeable other in relation to curriculum, I was uneasy with the fact that I had never had to teach pupils remotely (due to pandemic-related school closures) the way the teachers were required to. Furthermore, due to my lack of experience in this regard, I was acutely aware of the associated risk of being perceived as a “naïve out-of-touch visitor” (Kubiak et al., 2015 p.85) who lacked legitimacy or relevance. Suchman (1994, p.25) articulates this experience as broker succinctly, where the broker enters “onto territory in which we are unfamiliar and to some significant extent therefore unqualified”. In order to transform my discomfort into something constructive, the beginning of each LS meeting took the form of a structured check-in with all participants. The aim of this was to build rapport by inviting teachers to share and reflect on their ongoing experiences of remote teaching. Upon further reflection, I realised that this use of time also supported teachers to face a shared problem, start collaborative work and build a group

identity. Akkerman and Bruining (2016, p. 246) term this process “transformation” and identify it as a key learning mechanism associated with boundary crossing

Concluding Thoughts

Framed by sociocultural learning theories, this paper has offered some insights into the challenges experienced by a LS practitioner in brokering multilevel boundary crossings during their facilitation of an online LS. The structured protocols of LS acted not just as a boundary object, but also as a necessary scaffold for the author to maintain the personal fortitude required to engage in effective brokering. Whilst challenging, the experience of engaging in an online LS has brought the author a sense of hope and excitement for what further potential this mode of LS holds, in terms of connecting teachers and supporting their ongoing achievement of agency.

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